

**THE EFFECT OF ENVIRONMENT ON THE FATIGUE DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT
IN NOTCHED CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES**

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ABSTRACT

Several destructive and non-destructive methods were used to study the effect of absorbed moisture and/or heat on the T-C fatigue properties of notched, $0^\circ/\pm 45^\circ$, CFRP laminates. The main objective was the understanding of fatigue damage propagation around notches (sharp slits, and circular holes), under hot and/or wet environments. The fatigue performance of the notched laminates was mainly assessed by means of residual strength measurements. It was found that the shape and extent of fatigue damage around the notches is highly dependent upon the environments considered. Furthermore, it was shown that the residual strength or fatigue life depends upon the lay-up for a given environment.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon fibre composites are increasingly used in aircraft structures, therefore it is important to understand the influence of environment on their properties. Such likely environments are moisture and/or elevated temperature. Furthermore, such structures are subjected to a range of loading conditions, one of the most extreme ones being the tension-compression fatigue.

In the present study the T-C fatigue performance of two material lay-ups typical of composite wing-skins was evaluated in a range of environments combining temperature and/or moisture. The study involved cut-outs, such as sharp notches and circular holes, and assessment of the effect of the damage upon the residual strength.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAMME

Materials

Sixteen ply laminates were prepared from XAS/914C prepreg with the following lay-ups:

lay-up 'A' $(+45/-45/0_3/+45/-45/0)_s$
 lay-up 'B' $(0/+45/-45/0_2/+45/-45/0)_s$

Notches in the form of sharp 10mm slits or circular 5mm diameter holes were cut in coupons which measured 50mm wide by 250mm long. The specimens prepared with lay-up 'B' contained only sharp notches.

A series of plain (unnotched) coupons measuring 25mm x 250mm were also prepared.

Experimental Conditions

After preparation half of the total number of specimens were stored in an environmental cabinet at 60°C 84% RH until saturation and the remainder were stored at room temperature in a dessicator containing silica gel. The former are designated "wet" while the latter are designated "dry".

Mechanical Testing

Static Tests: Plain and notched coupons were loaded to failure in tension. Notched coupons were supported in an antibuckling guide and loaded to failure in compression. All tests were carried out at room temperature (RT), 90°C and 130°C. Typically, three specimens were tested in each condition to obtain average data.

Fatigue Tests: Notched specimens were supported in the antibuckling guide and subjected to reversed axial fatigue loading ($R = -1$) at a frequency of 20 Hz and remote strain amplitudes of 0.3% for the sharp notch and 0.4% for the circular hole. These strain levels were chosen to give significant damage after 10^3 cycles and a life in excess of 10^6 cycles.

Coupons with lay-up 'A' were subjected to fatigue loading at RT and 90°C, for 10^3 and 10^5 cycles. In the case of lay-up 'B' only fatigue tests for 10^5 cycles at room temperature were conducted.

All elevated temperature tests were carried out in a purpose-built circulating hot air chamber. This tended to provide a dry environment which led to some drying out of the wet specimens. However, measurements showed that in the worst case (1.5 hrs of testing at 90°C) the moisture content fell from a typical saturated level of 1.4% by weight to about 1.1%. Furthermore, slicing the specimens showed that this loss was mainly confined to the outer plies.

Following fatigue, specimens were non-destructively examined and residual tensile and compressive strengths were measured. These tests were carried out at RT, 90°C and 130°C.

Proof Loading: A series of notched specimens were loaded in either tension or compression to about 90% of their average strength. The resulting damage around the notch was examined using the C-scan. This series of

tests also included specimens which had been fatigued as described above.

Damage Detection

A range of damage detection techniques were used to characterise the damage induced around the notches. These include C-scan, X-ray, microscopic and deply techniques.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Mechanical Tests

All results are summarised in Figures 1a,b,c. These take the form of histograms showing both the tensile and compressive strengths - the compressive strength shown as negative. Each bar represents the average of three or two specimens which were virgin or fatigued respectively. The results from the plain tensile tests are also shown in these figures. Only values for the dry and wet cases at RT are presented, since tests at elevated temperatures failed to provide valid results. For clarity the spread of results from specimens of each test condition are not shown. The larger values of spread usually corresponded to the case of circular holes at elevated temperatures, and were typically of the order of 5% in tension and up to about 10% in compression.

Damage Detection

The penetrant-enhanced X-ray technique gave a clear indication of the damage around the notches. Figure 2 shows representative fatigue damage for both types of notches stress level and lay-up in a range of environments. The examples shown in this figure were chosen to highlight the different damage mechanisms occurring with the view to assessing the effect on the residual strength. Detailed discussion is presented below.

The C-scan technique provided a convenient method of detecting damage growth under proof loading. Examples of such damage development are illustrated in Figures 3i,ii, for the circular hole and sharp notch respectively.

The microscopic sectioning technique provided a clear view of the through-thickness location of the damage. Figure 4 shows some examples which were chosen to illustrate the effect of lay-up on the nature and extent of damage.

The deply technique was used for determining individual ply damage as well as the precise through-thickness location and extent of delamination. Gold chloride enhancing agent was used for marking the delaminations and fibre splits, even though appropriate lighting and a low magnification microscope had to be used for clear identification. In general, the damage documentation took the form of recorded personal observations, therefore no pictures are presented here.

(a) Circular hole

(c) Sharp notch, lay-up 'B'

(b) Sharp notch, lay-up 'A'

Figure 1. Residual strengths after T-C fatigue at $\pm 30\text{kN}$ and $\pm 20\text{kN}$, for circular holes and sharp notches respectively.

(a) "Wet" hole
Hot - Fatigue
 10^3 cycles, $\pm 30\text{kN}$

(b) "Wet" hole
RT - Fatigue
 10^5 cycles, $\pm 30\text{kN}$

(c) "Dry" hole
RT - Fatigue
 10^5 cycles, $\pm 30\text{kN}$

(d)
"Wet" slit, lay-up 'A'
Hot - Fatigue
 10^5 cycles, $\pm 20\text{kN}$

(e)
"Dry" slit, lay-up 'A'
Hot - Fatigue
 10^5 cycles, $\pm 20\text{kN}$

(f)
"Wet" slit, lay-up 'B'
Hot - Fatigue
 10^5 cycles, $\pm 20\text{kN}$

(g)
"Dry" slit, lay-up 'A'
RT - Fatigue
 1.4×10^6 cycles, $\pm 20\text{kN}$

(h)
"Dry" slit, lay-up 'A'
RT - Fatigue
 1.3×10^5 cycles, $\pm 26\text{kN}$

(i)
"Dry" slit, lay-up 'A'
RT - Fatigue
 2.5×10^6 cycles, $\pm 15\text{kN}$

Figure 2. X-rays of fatigue damage in various conditions.

(a) "Dry",
undamaged

(b) "Dry",
 $90^\circ - 10^5$

(c) "Wet",
RT - 10^5

130° Tension

RT - Tension

RT - Compression

(i) Circular holes

(a) "Dry",
undamaged

(b) "Wet",
undamaged

(c) "Dry",
RT - 10^5

RT - Tension

RT - Tension

RT - Tension

(ii) Sharp notches, lay-up 'A'

Figure 3. C-scans before and after proof loading of
damage and undamaged notched specimens.

Figure 4. Micrographs, for sharp notch, after 10^5 cycles hot (90°C) fatigue. The notch tip line is indicated by the arrows.

DISCUSSION

Since environmental conditioning is an important factor in the present study it is pertinent to mention briefly the reported effects, as found in the literature, of absorbed moisture and/or heat on the mechanical behaviour. These are:

1. As a result of moisture content (in epoxy resins) there is a noticeable reduction in the glass transition temperature - T_g , [1,2].
2. High temperature and/or moisture content increase the plasticity of the matrix, [1,3].
3. Moisture content reduces the thermal residual stresses by swelling, [4].
4. High temperature and/or moisture content reduce the interlaminar shear strength - ILSS, [1,5].

Key types of damage are presented in Figure 2. Figures 2a,b, show the damage around a circular hole characterised by two well defined longitudinal splits tangential to the hole containing an area of delamination. The extent of the splits depends on the number of fatigue cycles (but also on the environment, compare Figure 2c). Microscopic examination and deply showed that the delamination was primarily between the 0° and the $\pm 45^\circ$ layers. Such damage was typical of a range of conditions, e.g.

- a) Low (10^3) cycle fatigue of dry and wet specimens, cold (RT) and hot (90°C).
- b) Intermediate number of fatigue cycles (10^5) in wet specimens, cold.
- c) After tensile proof loading of undamaged specimens at elevated temperatures, e.g. Figure 3i(a).

Since this kind of damage is confined within a region defined by the width of the notch, it might be expected to reduce or even eliminate the original stress concentration due to the hole and thus increase both the tensile and compressive strengths. Indeed this is apparent in Figure 1a.

The development of lateral secondary longitudinal splits together with an increase in length of the primary splits are depicted in Figure 2c. This type of damage is usually observed in all moderate and high fatigue cycle conditions. However, the length and/or density of the secondary longitudinal and 45° splits depend on the number of fatigue cycles as well as the environment. In general, fatigue tends to increase these splits whereas moisture and/or temperature tend to suppress them. The increase of secondary longitudinal and 45° splits is usually followed by some lateral delamination mainly between the first $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° layers. Provided that the lateral delamination is limited, such damage is also beneficial in both tension and compression. In contrast, when the lateral delamination spreads, the split 0° fibres lose flexural support and this results in a poor compressive strength. Some of the 0° fibre bundles local to the hole can also fail during fatigue (in compression) and that can result in both poor tensile and compressive residual strength or indeed give rise to fatigue failure.

It is perhaps worthwhile mentioning at this point that the lateral support on the load bearing 0° fibres can also be reduced when the matrix is softened, in which case the compressive residual strength is decreased. The results of Figure 1a show that indeed this is the case, especially when temperature and moisture effects are combined.

Figure 2d shows a form of damage around a sharp notch consisting of two primary longitudinal splits and an area of delamination in-between. Like the hole this delamination is mainly between the 0° and $\pm 45^\circ$ plies. In addition, some secondary 45° splitting is also present. This kind of damage is typical of only one fatigue condition, namely hot-fatigue of wet specimens in lay-up 'A'. As in the case of holes, this damage has in general beneficial effects on both tensile and compressive residual strengths. However, the effect of the blunting is greater in this case such that an increase in tensile strength of almost 40%, Figure 1b, was recorded. Based on net section stresses this damage appears to almost eliminate the stress concentration effects of the notches.

In order to demonstrate that the fatigue damage growth around a hole is similar to that of a sharp notch, in the hot-wet condition, a limited programme of fatigue of wet coupons containing 10mm circular holes was performed. The C-scans in Figure 5a,b, show that (lay-up 'A') sharp notch and the 10mm circular hole appear to have identical damage characteristics and growth rates. Figure 5c, however, shows that under identical fatigue conditions lay-up 'B' behaves in a different manner yielding a very short fatigue life. The difference in damage between lay-ups 'A' and 'B' is also very well illustrated in the X-rays of Figure 2d,f.

The behaviour illustrated in Figure 2d may be contrasted to that in Figure 2e. In the latter, the primary longitudinal splits are accompanied by 45° splits, mainly associated with the notch tip, Figure 4a. A series of secondary splits develop along the 45° directions together with an area of delamination giving rise to the characteristic butterfly damage shape. A very similar damage to that in Figure 2e is the one in Figure 2i with additional secondary 0° splits. This kind of damage is typical of most fatigue cases at moderate and low stress levels for intermediate and high number of

(a) 10mm circular hole

(b) 10mm sharp notch, lay-up 'A'

(c) 10mm sharp notch, lay-up 'B'

Figure 5. Hot (90°C) fatigue of "wet" specimens at $\pm 30\text{kN}$ and $\pm 20\text{kN}$ for circular holes and sharp notches respectively.

fatigue cycles respectively, with the exception of the hot-wet case of lay-up 'A'. Such damage usually results in an increase in residual tensile strength, Figure 1b,c, since no load bearing fibres are lost. The effect on the residual compressive strength, however, depends upon the lateral extent of the delamination and secondary longitudinal splits.

Figure 2g represents a further stage in the damage development of Figure 2e. Here secondary longitudinal splits are well developed, extensive delamination has occurred and some load bearing fibres have failed. This kind of damage is observed in most cases of moderate and high cycles respectively, but is apparent earliest in lay-up 'B', Figure 4. In this case the effect of such damage on the residual tensile strength depends mainly upon the loss of load bearing fibres. In general, the residual tensile strength increases to a peak as damage occurs and falls with the occurrence of fibre fracture. The residual compressive strength depends on the number of broken fibres together with the lateral extent of delamination associated with secondary longitudinal splits. Equally, softening of the matrix, either due to temperature and/or moisture, reduces the compressive residual (and static) strengths.

The effects of stress level (amplitude) upon the damage mechanisms is well illustrated in Figures 2h,i. At high stress levels the damage tends to propagate laterally across the specimen as a result of matrix cracking in the off-axis plies together with some 0° fibre failure, Figure 2h. At lower stress levels longitudinal splits constitute the primary mode of damage, where the stress on the off-axis plies has not been high enough to initiate any significant transverse damage, Figure 2i. The stress concentration effects of the notch tend to be eliminated and damage progresses along the primary splits. Thus any factors which reduce the load borne by the 45° plies will promote longitudinal splitting, and hence result in improved tensile and compressive strengths. Such factors are:

- a) lay-up,
- b) fatigue amplitude,
- c) notch shape (stress concentration factor),
- d) absorbed moisture and/or temperature.

Ultimately if the in-plane shear stiffness is sufficiently degraded, constraint effects between 0° and 45° plies are eliminated. This is very well illustrated in Figure 3i(a & b). In the case of Figure 3i(a) high temperature causes longitudinal splitting, whereas in Figure 3i(b) even though the longitudinal splitting is present to start with, lateral damage appears to grow on application of tensile load at RT. Similarly, in the case of the sharp notch (lay-up 'A'), Figures 3ii(a & b) show that lateral delamination and 45° splitting occurred in the dry specimen, whereas 0° primary splitting and delamination within has occurred in the wet specimen, after tensile proof loading at RT.

The proof loading programme showed that, in the case of the hole, damage under tensile loading occurred mainly under hot conditions, whereas under compressive loading the contrary was true, Figure 3i(a & c). In the case of the sharp notch detectable damage grew only after tensile loading and mainly in the undamaged specimens Figures 3ii.

Microscopic examination showed that most of the fatigue damage occurs at the surface plies in all fatigue conditions with an initial suppression of damage in the wet specimens, which is thought to be due to relaxation of the thermal residual stresses.

CONCLUSIONS

The effects of temperature and moisture on the matrix considered are:

1. Temperature and/or moisture reduce the in-plane shear stiffness.
2. Moisture lowers the Tg of the matrix.
3. Matrix becomes softer with temperature and/or moisture.
4. Moisture reduces the thermally induced stresses during curing, by swelling.

The effects of environment and loading on the fatigue performance are:

1. Reduction of the constraint between 0° and 45° layers, by means of shear stiffness changes, leads to blunting of the notches (longitudinal splitting) and consequently improved residual strengths.
2. Softening of the matrix and lateral (widthwise) delamination growth lead to 0° fibre failure by buckling and hence poor compressive residual strength.
3. The lateral growth of fatigue damage mainly depends upon the percentage stress carried by the off-axis plies which in turn depends upon the stress concentration and load amplitude.

The fatigue performance under adverse environments is highly dependent on lay-up.

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ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This work has been supported by the Procurement Executive, Ministry of Defence.